

```

# Analysis of Intensity-Duration-Frequency-Curves with R
# Reset del workspace
rm(list = ls(all = TRUE))

# Set della cartella di lavoro
setwd("C:/Users/Paolo Turri/Desktop/IDROLOGIA 2017/Centa")

# Files contenuti nella cartella di lavoro
list.files()

# Definizioni Funzioni di Gumbel e Chi
#GumbelMoments estimates the parameters of a Gumbel CDF using the moements method
# x is the data set which is supposed to have a Gumbel CDF
GumbelMoments <- function(x){
  mlh <- mean(x);
  varlh <- var(x);
  eulergamma <-0.577215114901512810101510900810111042159115;
  blh <- sqrt(6*varlh)/pi;
  c(mlh - blh*eulergamma,blh)
}

# chi.test is a simple and stupid function to estimate the chi square residual
# q is the set of probabilities (including 0 and 1 over which partition the data)
# qtls are the quantiles correspondent to q (excluding 0 and 1)
# dat are the data used

chi.test <- function(q,qtls,dat){
  expected <- diff(q)*length(dat);
  ecdfh <- ecdf(sort(dat));
  c(ecdfh(qtls),1)*length(dat) - c(0,ecdfh(qtls))*length(dat) -> observed;
  sum((observed- expected)^2/(expected))
}

# Lettura dati da file .txt
read.table("centa.txt",header=TRUE) -> data
data
data[,1] -> anno
anno
data[,2]->datalh
datalh
mean(datalh,na.rm=TRUE) #media sulle misurazioni valide
mean(datalh)
summary(datalh) #dati statistici

# Eliminazione di valori NA
is.na(datalh)
!is.na(datalh)
anno <-anno[!is.na(datalh)]
anno #anni con misurazioni valide
datalh[!is.na(datalh)]
datalh <-datalh[!is.na(datalh)]
datalh

# Grafico precipitazioni annuali e istogramma
plot(anno,datalh,xlab="anno",ylab="h [mm]",main="Precipitazioni max annuali di durata 1h",col="blue",
     ,lwd="3",type="l")
hist(datalh,xlab="h [mm]",ylab="Frequenza",col="gold",main="Pioggia 1h")

# ECDF
ecdf(datalh) -> ecdf1h
ecdf1h
plot(ecdf1h,xlab="h [mm]",main="ECDF 1h")

# Metodo dei Momenti
GumbelMoments(datalh) -> glh
glh
seq(from=0,to=60,by=1) ->x
library("evd")
plot(ecdf1h,xlab="h [mm]",ylab="Fr[H < h]", main="ECDF piogge orarie")
lines(x,pgumbel(x,loc=glh[1],scale=glh[2]),lwd=2,col="red")

# Metodo della verosomiglianza
library("MASS")
fitdistr(datalh,densfun=dgumbel,start=list(loc=glh[1],scale=glh[2])) -> m1lh
m1lh
m1lh$estimate
m1lh$sd
m1lh$estimate["loc"]
m1lh$estimate[1]
plot(ecdf1h,xlab="h [mm]",ylab="Fr[H < h]", main="ECDF piogge orarie")
lines(x,pgumbel(x,loc=glh[1],scale=glh[2]),lwd=2,col="red")
lines(x,pgumbel(x,loc=m1lh$estimate["loc"],scale=m1lh$estimate["scale"]),lwd=2,col="dark green")

# Metodo dei minimi quadrati (non linear)
sorteddata <-sort(datalh)
h1 <- data.frame("x"=sorteddata,"y"=ecdf1h(sorteddata))
nls(data=h1,y ~ exp(-exp(-(x-a)/b)),start=list(a=10,b=5)) -> dt1h1

```

```
coefficients(dt1hl)
coefficients(dt1hl) ["a"]
is.numeric(coefficients(dt1hl) ["a"])
length(sorteddata)
lines(x,pgumbel(x,loc=coefficients(dt1hl) ["a"],scale=coefficients(dt1hl) ["b"]),lwd=2,col="dark blue")

#Test di Pearson

# Pearson sui minimi quadrati
alhl <-coefficients(dt1hl) ["a"]
blhl <-coefficients(dt1hl) ["b"]

q <- c(0,0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8,1)
qq <- qgumbel(q[-c(1,6)],loc=alhl,scale=blhl)
print("Chi quadro sui minimi quadrati")
chi.test(q,qq,data1h)

# Pearson per il metodo dei momenti
c(0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8)
qq <- qgumbel(q[-c(1,6)],loc=glh[1],scale=glh[2])
print("Chi quadro metodo dei momenti")
chi.test(q,qq,data1h)

# Pearson per la verosomiglianza
qq <- qgumbel(c(0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8),loc=m1h$estimate["loc"],scale=m1h$estimate["scale"])
print("Chi quadro verosomiglianza")
chi.test(q,qq,data1h)
```